

4-Quinazolones. Part I. Some Reactions of the Activated Methyl Group in 2-Methyl-3-Phenyl-4-Quinazolone

Buddha Deo Singh and D. N. Chaudhury

Compounds derived from 2-methyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone are described.

The methyl group in 2-methyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₃) is activated in the manner to be expected from the analogy with 2-methyl-4-quinazolone, the benzal derivatives of which have been reported¹. Reaction of electrophillic reagents should be catalysed by alkali through the production of the resonance-stabilized anion (A) and by acid, through prototopic change, to the tautomer (B).

Thus, condensation of (I; R=CH₃) with benzaldehyde and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde in the presence of acetic acid-acetic anhydride yielded 2-styryl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH=CH Ph) and 2-*p*-nitrostyryl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH=CH- C₆H₄ NO₂-*p*) respectively; alkaline catalyst, pyridine, effected the condensation with chloral to give 2-(α, α, α-trichloro-β-hydroxy-γ-propyl)-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂-CH(OH)-CCl₃).

Furthermore, the 2-methyl group was oxidised by SeO₂ to 3-phenyl-4-quinazolone-2-carboxaldehyde (I; R=CHO) which was characterised by its phenylhydrazone (I; R=CH=N NH Ph), 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (I; R=CH=N NH C₆H₃-di-NO₂-2':4'), and oxime (I; R=CH:NOH) derivatives. The aldehyde (I; R=CHO) readily condensed with aniline to afford 3-phenyl-4-quinazolone-2-carboxaldehyde anil (I; R=CHNPh), and with the quinazolone itself (I; R=CH₃) to furnish the *bis* compound(II). The aldehyde,

on oxidation with alkaline silver oxide, yielded 3-phenyl-4-quinazolone-2-carboxylic acid (I; R=COOH) which Paal and Krecke² failed to obtain by the oxidation of 3,4-dihydro-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazoline with permanganate. Since 3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=H) was the sole product of oxidation, they concluded that during oxidation, the intermediate formed was the acid (I; R=COOH) but being unstable it readily decarboxylated. We are unable to agree with their observation as we have prepared this acid and its sodium salt in good yields, and they are stable. The failure on the part of the earlier workers may be attributed to the vigorous condition of oxidation they employed.

Interaction of (I; R=CH₃) with NBS formed 2-bromomethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂Br) which with potassium acetate in DMF gave 2-acetoxymethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂OAc). It was deacetylated with sodium methoxide to afford 2-hydroxymethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂OH). 2-Methoxymethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂OCH₃) and 2-phenoxyethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂OPh) were obtained when the bromo compound (I; R=CH₂Br) was treated with sodium methoxide and sodium phenoxide respectively. Potassium cyanide in DMF reacted with the bromo compound to afford 2-cyanomethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂CN) in good yield (I; R=CH₂Br) with pyridine or hexamine formed the pyridinium salt (I; R=CH₂NC₅H₅Br) and hexamine salt (I; R=CH₂.N₄C₆H₁₂Br) respectively. The latter, however, could not be transformed into the aldehyde (I; R=CHO) according to Sommelet method³. Similar negative results⁴ have been reported with several heterocyclic derivatives.

Interestingly, derivatives of the aldehyde (I; R=CHO) were obtained from the 2-bromomethyl compound (I; R=CH₂Br). Thus interaction of the bromo compound with excess hydroxylamine and phenylhydrazine provided 3-phenyl-4-quinazolone-2-carboxaldehyde oxime (I; R=CH:NOH) and phenylhydrazone derivative (I; R=CH:NNHPh) respectively. These are identical with the specimens obtained directly from the aldehyde (I; R=CHO). With excess hydrazine, the bromo quinazolone (I; R=CH₂Br) gave 3-phenyl-4-quinazolone-2-carboxaldehyde hydrazone (I; R=CH:NNH₂) which could not be synthesised from the aldehyde (I; R=CHO) upon reaction with hydrazine. Similar failure to prepare the hydrazone from 5-uracil carboxaldehyde has been recorded⁴. The formation of the derivatives of the aldehyde (I; R=CHO) from the bromomethyl compound (I; R=CH₂Br) is noteworthy in view of the fact that substituted benzyl chlorides under similar conditions are not converted into aldehyde derivatives⁵. But the conversion of the bromomethyl quinazolone (I; R=CH₂Br) with hydrazine, hydroxylamine, and phenylhydrazine resembles the reported reaction⁴ of 5- and 6-halogenomethyl purine with hydrazines and hydroxylamine, the transformation of 2-chloromethyl pyridine to 2-pyridine aldoxime⁶, and the reaction of phenacyl bromides with the hydrazines⁷. The mechanism of such reactions has been elaborated^{4,6}.

2. C. Paal and Fr. Krecke, *Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 3055.

3. M. Sommelet, *Compt. rend.*, 1913, **157**, 852; S. J. Angyal, *Org. Reactions*, 1954, **8**, 197.

4. A. Giner-Sorolla and A. Bendich, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 4239.

5. R. V. Rothenberg, *Ber.*, 1893, **26**, 865; M. Busch and B. Weiss, *ibid.*, 1900, **33**, 2701.

6. F. A. Daniher, B. E. Hackley (Jr.) and A. B. Ash, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2709.

7. S. Hauptmann, K. D. Seidig and H. Wilde, *Angew. Chem.*, 1965, **77**, 678; S. C. Bell, R. J. McCaully and S. J. Childress, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 2889.

EXPERIMENTAL*

2-Methyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₃). Anthranilic acid (17.1 g.) was dissolved in water (125 ml.) containing anhydrous Na₂CO₃ (6.6 g.), the solution filtered and treated with acetic anhydride (12.5 ml.) with stirring when the *sodium salt* of acetylanthranilic acid precipitated out at once. The mixture was cooled to 15°, the solid filtered off, washed with a little ice-water and dried in an oven at 110°. Yield 23 g., m.p. 285° (lit.⁸, m.p. 285°).

To a mixture of the sodium salt (19 g.), toluene (125 ml.) and aniline (9 ml.), was added with shaking a solution of PCl₃ (2.9 ml.) in toluene (25 ml.) during 15 min. and then refluxed in an oil bath at 120-25° for 2 hr. with frequent shaking. After cooling, the precipitate was collected, washed with ether, treated with dil. NaOH and filtered. The solid was washed thoroughly with water and crystallised twice from ethanol to give the quinazolone as colorless prismatic needles (20 g.), m.p. 148-9° (lit.⁹, m.p. 146-7°)

2-Styryl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH=CH-Ph). A solution of the foregoing quinazolone (1.18 g.) and benzaldehyde (0.52 ml.) in a mixture of glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) was refluxed for 2 hr. Most of the solvent was distilled off and the residual liquid was poured into water when white solid precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to afford the *styryl derivative* as colorless needles (1.2 g.), m.p. 193-4°. (Found: C, 81.17; H, 5.23. C₂₂H₁₆N₂O requires C, 81.48; H, 4.93%.)

2-p-Nitrostyryl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH=CH-C₆H₄-NO₂-*p*). *2-Methyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone* (1.18 g.) and *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.76 g.) in acetic anhydride (15 ml.) was refluxed for 1 hr. when yellow crystals separated out. These were filtered after cooling, washed with water, air-dried and recrystallised from chloroform to yield the *p-nitrostyryl derivative* as yellow needles (1.4 g.), m.p. 285°. (Found: N, 11.60. C₂₂H₁₅N₃O₃ requires N, 11.38%.)

2-(α, α, α-Trichloro-β-hydroxy-γ-propyl)-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂-CH(OH)-CCl₃).—A mixture of the quinazolone (I; R=CH₃) (5.9 g.), chloral (4.61 g.) and pyridine (0.4 ml.) was heated at 80° for 1 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was diluted with water, the solid which precipitated was collected and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed successively with water, dilute NaHCO₃, water, dil. HCl, and water, and was then dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the solvent and trituration of the resulting pink oil with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) gave a colorless solid which on recrystallisation twice from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) gave the *trichloro compound* as colorless needles (5.6 g.), m.p. 120-22°, (Found: C, 53.41; H, 3.57; Cl, 28.03. C₁₇H₁₃N₂O₂Cl₃ requires C, 53.19; H, 3.39; Cl, 27.77%.)

3-Phenyl-4-quinazolone-2-carboxaldehyde (I; R=CHO). A solution of the quinazolone (I; R=CH₃) (5 g.) in hot ethanol (30 ml.) was treated with freshly prepared SeO₂ (4.5 g.), refluxed for 4 hr. and filtered hot. On cooling, the solution deposited off-white needles which

*All m.ps are uncorrected.

8. M. Murayama and T. Watanabe, Nippon Shinyaku Co., Ltd. Japan Patent, No. 5939 of 1964; *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, **61**, 13328.
9. G. Serventi and R. Marchesi, *Bell. Sci. fac. chim. ind. Bologna*, 1957, **15**, 117; *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, **52**, 9147.

were collected. The complete removal of selenium was effected by recrystallising the product four times from ethanol and filtering the hot alcoholic solution each time. The pure *aldehyde* was obtained as colorless felted needles (2.5 g.), m.p. 208°, with previous sintering at 201°. (Found: C, 71.82; H, 4.25; N, 10.9. $C_{15}H_{10}N_2O_2$ requires C, 72.0; H, 4.0; N, 11.2%). It readily reduces Fehling's solution and Tollen's reagent.

Its *2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone*, prepared by the method of Shine¹⁰, formed deep red needles (from diglyme), m.p. 280° (decomp.). (Found: N, 19.34; $C_{21}H_{14}N_6O_5$ requires N, 19.53%).

Its *phenylhydrazone*, prepared by the interaction with phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and potassium acetate in alcoholic solution, formed yellow needles (from benzene), m.p. 245°. (Found: N, 16.23. $C_{21}H_{16}N_4O$ requires N, 16.47%).

Its *oxime derivative*, prepared by the pyridine method, formed colorless felted needles (from ethyl acetate), m.p. 205-6°. (Found: N, 15.59. $C_5H_{11}N_3O_2$ requires N, 15.85%).

3-Phenyl-4-quinazolone-3-carboxaldehyde anil (I; R=CH=N-Ph).—The aldehyde (I; R=CHO) (0.5 g.) dissolved in hot ethanol (15 ml.) was treated with aniline (0.2 ml.) and refluxed for 1 hr. Most of the alcohol was distilled off, the oily residue triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) to furnish a solid which was collected and washed with ether. Crystallisations from benzene gave the pure *anil* as off-white needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 132-3°. (Found: N, 12.74. $C_{21}H_{15}N_3O$ requires N, 12.92%).

Bis-2-methylidene-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (II). A mixture of the aldehyde (I; R=CHO) (0.125 g.) and the quinazolone (I; R=CH₃) (0.12 g.) in a mixture of glacial acetic acid (7 ml.) and acetic anhydride (2 ml.) was refluxed when a clear solution obtained; after 15 min. yellow crystals began to separate. The mixture was refluxed for a total period of 1 hr., cooled, the yellow crystals were filtered off and washed with ether. Crystallisation from acetic acid afforded the *bis compound* (II) as long yellow needles (0.12 g.), m.p. >290°. (Found: N, 12.17. $C_{30}H_{20}N_4O_2$ requires N, 12.39%).

3-Phenyl-4-quinazolone-2-carboxylic acid (I; R=COOH). 15% NaOH solution (4 ml.) was added to a solution of AgNO₃ (2.47 g.) in water (14 ml.) when black AgOH precipitated, and to this mixture was added the aldehyde (I; R=CHO) and refluxed. Silver mirror that deposited initially started disintegrating after 2 hr. and the reflux continued for a further period of 2 hr. The hot solution was filtered, cooled and acidified with dilute HCl when a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to yield the *acid* (I; R=COOH) as off-white tiny needles (1 g.), m.p. 191°. (Found: C, 67.48; H, 3.92; N, 10.48. $C_{15}H_{10}N_2O_3$ requires C, 67.67; H, 3.76; N, 10.52%). In one oxidation experiment, the hot filtrate after reflux, on cooling in an ice-chest, deposited the *sodium salt of the acid* (I; R=COONa), m.p. 139°, which on treatment with dil. HCl gave the *acid*, m.p. and mixed m.p. 191°.

2-Bromomethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂Br). A solution of the quinazolone (I; R=CH₃) (2.36 g.) was effected in carbon tetrachloride (10 ml.) by warming and to it was added freshly prepared NBS (1.78 g.) followed by benzoyl peroxide (0.02 g.), the reaction flask being kept close to an illuminated 60-watt lamp. It was refluxed on water bath

for 4 hrs., filtered hot from succinimide, and kept in the refrigerator overnight. The solid that deposited was filtered off, treated with a little acetone to dissolve away the unchanged starting material and the residue crystallised from ethanol to furnish the pure *bromomethyl compound* as off-white prisms (2 g.), m.p. 181°, with previous sintering at 179°. (Found: C, 57.31; H, 3.52; Br, 25.27. $C_{15}H_{11}N_2OBr$ requires C, 57.14; H, 3.49; Br, 25.39%).

2-Acetoxyethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂OAc). A solution of the preceding bromo compound (1 g.) in warm DMF (10 ml.) was treated with freshly fused potassium acetate (1.5 g.) and heated on water bath for 1 hr. It was then poured into ice-water and the precipitated solid filtered off, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. Crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) afforded the *acetate* as colorless needles (0.75 g.), m.p. 101°. (Found: C, 69.18; H, 4.95. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2O_3$ requires C, 69.39; H, 4.76%).

2-Hydroxymethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂OH). To a solution of the foregoing acetate (0.5 g.) in dry methanol (10 ml.) was added a solution of sodium methoxide (from 10 mg. of Na in 10 ml. methanol) and left over night at room temperature. Most of the methanol was distilled off and the residue treated with ice-water when white precipitate obtained. It was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give the *alcohol* as colorless needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 180°. (Found: N, 10.91. $C_{15}H_{12}N_2O_2$ requires N, 11.11%).

2-Methoxymethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂OCH₃). The bromo compound (I; R=CH₂Br) (1 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (0.115 g.) in dry methanol (20 ml.) and refluxed on water bath for 3 hr. Most of the solvent was distilled off and the residue treated with ice-water containing one drop of acetic acid when white solid precipitated. It was collected, washed with water and crystallised from methanol to yield the *methyl ether* as colorless needles (0.87 g.), m.p. 180-81°. (Found: C, 72.22; H, 5.45; N, 10.46. $C_{16}H_{14}N_2O_2$ requires C, 72.18; H, 5.26; N, 10.52%). It gave negative Bielstein test and depressed the m.p. (181°) of the starting bromo compound.

2-Phenoxyethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂OPh). A solution of the bromomethyl quinazolone (I; R=CH₂Br) (1 g.) in DMF (5 ml.) was treated with phenol (0.3 g.) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (2.3 g.) and set aside at room temperature over night. It was then poured into ice-water, the precipitated solid was collected and washed with water. Crystallisation from methanol afforded the *phenoxy compound* as colorless needles (0.85 g.), m.p. 136°. (Found: C, 76.77; H, 5.13. $C_{21}H_{16}N_2O_2$ requires C, 76.83; H, 4.87%).

2-Cyanomethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (I; R=CH₂CN). To a solution of the bromo compound (I; R=CH₂Br) (1 g.) in DMF (10 ml.) was added KCN (0.22 g.) and the mixture heated on water bath for 1.5 hr. It was then poured into ice-water, the precipitated solid filtered off and washed with water. Crystallisation from ethanol furnished the *cyanomethyl compound* as colorless needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 248-9°: (Found: N, 16.26. $C_{16}H_{11}N_3O$ requires N, 16.09%).

2-Pyridiniummethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone bromide (I; R=CH₂-NC₅H₅Br). (I; R=CH₂Br) (1 g.) in pyridine (15 ml.) was shaken at room temperature when a clear solution obtained; within a few min. a precipitate separated out from the solution which was filtered off and washed with ether. Crystallisation from ethanol gave the *pyridinium salt* as pink rhombic prisms (0.8 g.), m.p. 243-4°. (Found: Br, 20.43. $C_{20}H_{16}N_3OBr$ requires Br, 20.3%).

2-Hexamethylene tetraammoniummethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone bromide (I; $R=CH_2$, $N_4C_6H_{12}Br$). A solution of hexamine (1.5 g.) and the bromomethyl quinazolone (I; $R=CH_2Br$) (3 g.) in chloroform (15 ml.) was heated on water bath for 15 min. when crystalline solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with ether and crystallised from large volume of ethyl acetate to give the *salt* as micro prisms (3 g.), m.p. 185-7°. (Found: N, 18.39. $C_{21}H_{23}N_6$ OBr requires N, 18.46%).

3-Phenyl-4-quinazolone-2-carboxaldehyde oxime (I; $R=CH:NOH$). A hot solution of the bromomethyl compound (I; $R=CH_2Br$) in ethanol (20 ml.) was added to a warm solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.6 g.) and potassium acetate (1.63 g.) in water (2 ml.), and the mixture refluxed for 4 hr. After cooling to room temperature, insoluble inorganic material was filtered off, most of the alcohol distilled off from the filtrate and the remaining solution treated with ice-water. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. Crystallisation from ethyl acetate furnished to *oxime* as colorless felted needles (0.7 g.), m.p. 205-6°, underpressed on admixture with the specimen prepared earlier by the oximation of the aldehyde.

3-Phenyl-4-quinazolone-2-carboxaldehydephenylhydrazone (I; $R=CH=N.NHPh$). To a solution of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (2.4 g.) and potassium acetate (1.63 g.) in water (5 ml.) was added a hot solution of the bromoquinazolone (I; $R=CH_2Br$) (1 g.) in ethanol (20 ml.) and refluxed. After 15 min., crystalline solid separated, the mixture heated for a total period of 4 hr., and then ethanol (Ca. 10 ml.) was distilled off from the reaction mixture. The residue was poured into ice-water, the solid collected, air-dried and crystallised from benzene to yield the *phenylhydrazone derivative* as yellow needles (1 g.), m.p. 245°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained earlier directly from the aldehyde.

3-Phenyl-4-quinazolone-2-carboxaldehyde hydrazone (I; $R=CH=N.NH_2$). A solution of 2-bromomethyl-3-phenyl-4-quinazolone (1 g.) in hot ethanol (20 ml.) was treated with 80% hydrazine (0.7 ml.) and refluxed for 4 hr. The solution was concentrated and poured into ice-water. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. It was crystallised from benzene to afford the *hydrazone derivative* as colorless rods (0.7 g.), m.p. 195-6°. (Found: N, 21.07. $C_{15}H_{12}N_4O$ requires N, 21.21%).